

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS
PART XII. *CIS-TRANS* ISOMERISM IN COBALT BIGUANIDE
COMPLEXES. DIAMMINO HYDROXO-AMMINO-, DIAQUO-,
HYDROXO-AQUO-, DIACIDO- AND HYDROXO-ACIDO-
COBALTIC *BIS*BIGUANIDINIUM SALTS

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A series of basic and normal *trans*-diammino-cobaltic *bis*biguanidinium salts, namely, sulphate, chloride, bromide, iodide and nitrate has been prepared. Deamination and dehydration of these, followed in certain cases by hydrolysis, have led to the production of hydroxo-ammino, hydroxo-acido, hydroxo-aquo, diacido and diaquo cobaltic *bis*biguanidinium salts. Their *trans* configuration has been proved by the action of oxalic acid on the hydroxo-aquo cobaltic *bis*biguanidinium hydroxide of the series. While this hydroxide forms only the corresponding oxalate, the hydroxide of the *cis*-series, previously described by Rây and Ghosh, has been found to give an oxalato-cobaltic *bis*biguanidinium oxalate.

In Part X of this series Rây and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 1) have described the preparation of a diammino- and a hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic *bis*-biguanide complex which were found to possess a *cis* configuration on the basis of their properties and reactions. With a view to obtaining further evidences regarding the configuration of these complexes and to finding out methods for the preparation of their *trans* modification, the present investigation was undertaken. This has led to the isolation of the *trans* modification of a series of disubstituted cobalt *bis*biguanide complexes as described here. *Trans*-diammino-cobaltic *bis*biguanide complex was obtained by a modification of Rây and Ghosh's method for the preparation of the corresponding *cis* compound. This formed the starting substance for the preparation of the rest of the disubstituted *trans* complexes, viz., hydroxo-ammino-, diaquo-, hydroxo-aquo-, diacido- and hydroxo-acido-cobaltic *bis*biguanidinium compounds. The following diagrammatic scheme provides a synopsis of their formation, properties, reactions and inter-relation, as well as that of some of their *cis* modifications, previously described by Rây and Ghosh, for the sake of comparison.

It will be found that by the action of sodium thiosulphate the hydroxo-aquo derivative of both the series ultimately leads to the same product, an insoluble, non-electrolyte binuclear bridge compound, μ -thiosulphato-tetrakis *bis*biguanidinium dithiosulphato-dicobalt, already described by Rây and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*), which indicates a transformation of the *trans*-hydroxo-aquo complex into its isomeric *cis* form in the presence of H^+ ions.

The configurations of the two series have been definitely proved by the action of oxalic acid on their respective hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic *bis*biguanidinium hydroxide. The *cis* compound gives rise to an oxalato-oxalate, while its *trans* isomer yields only a hydroxo-aquo oxalate as is to be expected.

Trans-Series

The individual salts of the *trans*-diammino-*bis*-biguanidinium complex exhibit a characteristic difference in their composition. Thus, the chloro-, bromo- and iodo-sulphate of this complex are represented by the formulae,

where X stands for the complex ion, $[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2]^{+++}$ and BigH—one molecule of biguanide, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_5$.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. (a) *Diammino-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Hydroxo-sulphate.*
- (b) *Hydroxo-ammino-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Sulphate.*
- (c) *Hydroxo-sulphato-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Sulphate.*

Biguanide sulphate (13.2g.), dissolved in the least quantity (100 c.c.) of 1 : 1 ammonia (6*N*), was slowly added with stirring to that of 7.2 g. of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the smallest amount (15 c.c.) of water. The mixture, containing the yellow precipitate of cobaltous *bis*biguanidinium sulphate, was transferred to a flask; about 15 c.c. of liq. ammonia were then added and air was passed through the mixture till the yellow product turned red. The flask was warmed on the water-bath till the precipitate just dissolved. Some unoxidised yellow compound sometimes remained behind. This was filtered off and the filtrate, to which again about 12 c.c. of strong ammonia were added, was left overnight in a refrigerator in a well-stoppered vessel. Red crystals slowly separated from the solution. After 24 hours these were filtered and washed with 1 : 1 ammonia. The product was then recrystallised from warm ammoniacal water, washed first with dilute ammonia, then with alcohol saturated with ammonia gas, and finally dried in air. {Found : N, 38.02, 38.0; Co, 13.40, 13.25; SO_4 , 21.82, 21.37; H_2O , 8.09.

$[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2] \frac{\text{OH}}{\text{SO}_4} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 37.84; Co, 13.29; SO_4 , 21.62; H_2O , 8.10 per cent}.

The diammino-cobaltic *bis*biguanidinium hydroxosulphate forms red rectangular crystals, sparingly soluble in water. The solution reacts alkaline to litmus.

When heated to 80° the substance loses its water of crystallisation. At 90° one of the ammino groups is removed and at 100° the rest of ammonia is lost. From the dehydrated and deaminated product the whole of SO_4 is precipitated even in an ice-cold solution, showing that the product obtained by deamination is stable only in the solid state.

The substance dried at 80° to a constant weight gave the following results on analysis. {Found : N, 41.32; Co, 14.29.

$[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2] \frac{\text{OH}}{\text{SO}_4}$ requires N, 41.17; Co, 14.46 per cent}.

The product dried at 90° gave on analysis the following results. {Found : N, 39.13 ; Co, 14.97. $[(\text{NH}_3)(\text{OH})\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \text{SO}_4$, hydroxo-ammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate requires N, 39.39 ; Co, 15.10 per cent}.

The substance dried at 100° to a constant weight gave on analysis : Co, 15.72. $\left[(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \text{Co} \begin{array}{l} \text{OH} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{O} \end{array} \right] \text{SO}_3^{\prime\prime}$, hydroxo-sulphato-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate, requires Co, 15.78 per cent}.

Loss in weight suffered by the hydrated diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-sulphate at different temperatures is given in the following table.

TABLE I

Temp.	Wt. of subs.	Loss in wt.	Loss %.	Loss (calc.).
30° (room temp)	1.4026g.
80	1.8986	0.1040g.	8.09	8.10 (for 2H ₂ O)
90	1.2423	0.1603	11.87	11.93 (for 1NH ₃ & 2H ₂ O)
100	1.1947	0.2079	15.99	16.22 (for 2NH ₃ & 2H ₂ O)

2. (a) *Diammino-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Hydroxo-chloride.*

(b) *Hydroxo-chloro-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Chloride.*

The diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-chloride was prepared by the decomposition of the diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-sulphate with the calculated amount of barium chloride in the form of a saturated solution. On addition of alcohol to the cold filtrate, free from Ba⁺⁺, or SO₄^{''}, the substance was obtained in rose-coloured, needle-shaped crystals. These were filtered, washed free from the mother-liquor with ice-cold water followed by cold alcohol and finally dried in air. The substance was found to be more soluble than the diammino compound. The solution reacts alkaline to litmus. {Found : N, 43.64 ; Cl, 18.32 ; Co, 15.31 ; NH₃, 8.63 (by loss at 80°).

$\left[(\text{NH}_3)_2 \text{Co} (\text{BigH}^+)_2 \right] \frac{\text{OH}}{\text{Cl}_2}$, diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-chloride, requires N, 43.86 ; Cl, 18.54 ; Co, 15.39 ; NH₃, 8.88 per cent}.

When heated to 80° the substance lost both its amino groups and the product gave the following results on analysis. {Found: Co, 16.80.

$\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_{2} \\ \diagup \\ \text{Cl} \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}$, hydroxo-chloro-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium chloride, requires Co, 16.90 per cent}.

From the deaminated product the whole of the chlorine was precipitated as AgCl even in an ice-cold solution, indicating that the substance is stable only in the solid state.

3. *Diammino-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Hydroxo-nitrate*.—The diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-sulphate was decomposed by digestion with an equivalent quantity of barium nitrate in the form of a saturated solution. The filtrate, freed from Ba⁺⁺ and SO₄^{''}, was made ammoniacal and cooled with the addition of alcohol. Light rose-coloured, needle-shaped crystals of the hydroxo-nitrate separated from the solution. These were filtered, washed with ice-cold alcohol till free from the mother-liquor, and finally dried in air. The solution of the substance reacts alkaline to litmus.

{Found: N (besides that of NO₃), 36.49; Co, 12.68; NO₃, 26.80.
 $\left[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_{2} \right] \begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ (\text{NO}_3)_2 \end{array}$, 1.5H₂O requires N (excluding NO₃), 36.28; Co, 12.75; NO₃, 26.78 per cent}.

4. *Diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium chloro-sulphate* was obtained as light rose-coloured crystals by treating the diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-sulphate with ice-cold N-HCl added in drops till the supernatant liquid reacted slightly acidic to litmus. These were filtered and washed free from excess acid with alcohol. The product was purified by recrystallisation from ammoniacal water and subsequently dried in air. The solution of the substance reacts neutral to litmus. {Found: N, 37.52; Cl, 7.96; Co, 13.23; SO₄, 21.58.

$\left[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_{2} \right] \begin{array}{c} \text{Cl} \\ \text{SO}_4 \end{array}$, H₂O requires N, 37.84; Cl, 7.99; Co, 13.27; SO₄, 21.60 per cent}.

5. *Diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium bromo-sulphate* was obtained in the form of red rectangular prisms on cooling a solution of diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-sulphate mixed with twice its equivalent of ammonium bromide in the least quantity of warm ammoniacal water. The crystals were washed first with cold water, then with cold alcohol and finally dried in air. The substance reacts neutral to litmus. {Found: N, 31.50; Br, 30.07; Co, 11.06; SO₄, 8.90.

$\left[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_{2} \right]_2 \begin{array}{c} \text{Br}_4 \\ \text{SO}_4 \end{array}$, 3.5H₂O requires N, 31.43; Br, 29.99; Co, 11.04; SO₄, 8.98 per cent}.

6. *Diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium iodo-sulphate* was prepared in the same way as the above-described bromo-sulphate by using ammonium bromide. It forms red prismatic crystals which are less soluble than those of the corresponding bromo-sulphate. Its solution reacts neutral to litmus. {Found : N, 26.49 ; I, 40.09 ; Co, 9.34 ; SO₄, 7.52. $[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2 \text{SO}_4 \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 26.73 ; I, 40.42 ; Co, 9.38 ; SO₄ 7.64 per cent}.

Thus the complex bromo and iodo-sulphate differ in composition from the corresponding chloro-sulphate.

7. (a) *Diammino-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Sulphate.*
- (b) *Sulphato-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Sulphate.*

The diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate was obtained in light rose-coloured prismatic needles by one of the following methods :

(i) By cooling a solution of diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-sulphate in warm ammonia to which an excess of ammonium sulphate was added. The crystals that separated out were washed with ice-cold water followed by cold alcohol.

(ii) By the neutralisation of a suspension of diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-sulphate with ice-cold N-H₂SO₄, added in drops, till the supernatant solution was slightly acidic to litmus.

The product obtained by either of the above methods was purified by recrystallisation from warm ammoniacal water. It was then dried in air. Its solution reacts neutral to litmus. {Found : N, 30.61 ; Co, 10.85 ; SO₄, 26.45.

$[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2 (\text{SO}_4)_3, 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 30.71 ; Co, 10.78 ; SO₄, 26.33 per cent}.

The substance lost ten molecules of its water of crystallisation on dehydration over lime in an atmosphere of ammonia.

The product, dried at 85° to a constant weight, gave the following results on analysis : N, 38.41 ; Co, 13.39. $[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ requires N, 38.26 Co, 13.43 per cent.

When dried to a constant weight at 110° the product lost all its ammonia and gave on analysis Co, 14.48. $[(\text{SO}_4)\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ sulphato-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate, requires Co, 14.50 per cent.

The whole of the sulphate is precipitated from a cold solution of this dried product showing that the sulphato compound is stable only in the solid state.

The loss in weight suffered by the hydrated diammino-sulphate,

$\left[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+) \right]_2 (\text{SO}_4)_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at different temperatures is given in the following table.

TABLE II

Temp	Wt of substance.	Loss of wt.	% Loss.
30° (room temp.)	2.2889g.
85°	2.2086	0.0802g.	3.6 (calc. for $2\text{H}_2\text{O}=3.9$)
110°	2.1054	0.1835	7.5 (calc. for $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $2\text{NH}_3=7.66$)

8. (a) *Diammino-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Chloride.*

(b) *Dichloro-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Chloride.*

The diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium chloride was obtained by the decomposition of the diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate with the calculated quantity of barium chloride in the form of a saturated solution. The filtrate from barium sulphate on cooling gave light rose-coloured prismatic needles of the substance on addition of alcohol. The crystals were washed free from mother-liquor with cold alcohol and finally dried in air. The solution reacts acid to litmus.

{Found : N, 38.14 ; Cl, 24.39 ; Co, 13.37. $\left[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+) \right] \text{Cl}_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 38.40 ; Cl, 24.34 ; Co, 13.47 per cent.}

The substance on dehydration to a constant weight at 85° gave on analysis : N, 41.90 ; Co, 14.65. $\left[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+) \right] \text{Cl}_3$ requires N, 41.84 ; Co, 14.68 per cent.

The product obtained by drying to a constant weight at 110° gave on analysis : Co, 15.96. $\left[\text{Cl}_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+) \right] \text{Cl}$, dichloro-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium chloride, requires Co, 16.04 per cent. The substance thus lost both its ammonia molecules at 110°.

The whole of the chlorine is precipitated as AgCl from a cold solution of the product dried at 110°, indicating that the dichloro-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium chloride is stable only in the solid state.

The loss of weight suffered by the hydrated diammino-chloride at different temperatures is given in the following table.

TABLE III

Temp.	Wt. of substance.	Loss in wt.	% Loss.
30° (room temp.)	1.5111 g.
85°	1.3867	0.1224g.	8.10 (calc. for 2H ₂ O = 8.23)
110°	1.1727	0.3384	15.78 (calc. for 2H ₂ O & 2NH ₃ = 16.0)

TABLE IV

Equivalent conductivity of $[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{Cl}_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ *at* $33 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Dilution (v)	32	64	128	256	512	1024 litres
Λ_v	123.3	134.9	147.3	158.9	170.2	178.8 in mols

The values are rather quite high indicating partial hydrolysis into hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium chloride as shown below :

The equivalent conductivity of the substance, if unchanged, would lie near about 120 at infinite dilution like that of KCl.

9. *Diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium nitrate* was prepared by the decomposition of the corresponding complex sulphate with a saturated solution of barium nitrate. On adding alcohol to the ammoniacal ice-cold filtrate the substance was obtained in the form of light rose-coloured, prismatic needles. These were washed free from mother-liquor with cold alcohol and finally dried in air. Its solution reacts acid to litmus. {Found : N (excluding NO₃), 33.42 ; Co, 11.77 ; NO₃, 37.0.

$[(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2](\text{NO}_3)_3, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N (excluding NO₃), 33.67 ; Co, 11.81 ; NO₃, 37.27 per cent}.

10. *Hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate* separated as red crystals by the addition of alcohol to an ice-cold solution of hydroxo-sulphato-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate produced by the dehydration and deamination of diammino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-sulphate (*vide supra*).

It is very soluble in water and the solution reacts alkaline to litmus. The corresponding *cis*-isomer (*cf.* R&y and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*), on the other hand, like its chromium analogue, hydroxo-aquo-chromium *bi*-biguanidinium sulphate (R&y and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 353), is blue-violet in colour and sparingly soluble in water.

{Found : Co, 13.65 ; SO₄, 22.39. $\left[(\text{OH}) (\text{H}_2\text{O}) \text{Co} (\text{BigH}^+) _2 \right] \text{SO}_4, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 13.77 ; SO₄, 22.43 per cent}.

11. *Hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium chloride* was obtained in red violet needle-shaped crystals by one of the following methods :

(i) By slow evaporation in air of the filtrate from the decomposition of diammino-cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-sulphate* with barium chloride solution.

(ii) By recrystallisation from water of hydroxo-chloro-cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium chloride* produced by the deamination of diammino-cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium hydroxo-chloride* by heat.

The product obtained by either of the above methods was purified by recrystallisation from warm water. The solution of the substance reacts alkaline to litmus. {Found : N, 36.39 ; Cl, 18.30 ; Co, 15.17 ; H₂O, 9.24.

$\left[(\text{OH}) (\text{H}_2\text{O}) \text{Co} (\text{BigH}^+) _2 \right] \text{Cl}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 36.37 ; Cl, 18.44 ; Co, 15.31 ; H₂O, 9.35 per cent}.

The substance, when dried to a constant weight at 80°, loses all the water molecules and forms hydroxo-chloro-cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium chloride*, described above. (Found for the dried product : Co, 16.73. Calc. Co, 16.90 per cent).

By heating to 20°, therefore, not only the water of hydration but also that bound inside the complex zone is lost.

12. *Diaquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate* was obtained in the form of light rose-coloured prismatic needles by the addition of alcohol to an ice-cold solution of sulphato-cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium sulphate*, obtained by the deamination of diammino-cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium sulphate* (*vide supra*). It is very soluble in water and the solution reacts neutral to litmus. {Found : Co, 13.42 ; SO₄ 32.98.

$\left[(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \text{Co} (\text{BigH}^+) _2 \right]_2 (\text{SO}_4)_3$ requires Co, 13.37 ; SO₄, 32.65 per cent}.

13. *Diaquo cobaltic bisbiguanidinium chloride* was obtained as a red crystalline precipitate by passing dry HCl gas through an ice-cold saturated solution of dichloro cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium chloride*, obtained by the deamination of diammino cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium chloride* (*vide supra*). The passage of HCl gas should be stopped in time to prevent the decomposition of the substance. The product was filtered, washed free from HCl with cold alcohol and dried in air. The substance is very soluble in water and the solution reacts neutral to litmus. {Found : Cl, 26.13 ; Co, 14.61 ; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 8.79.

$\left[(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \text{Co} (\text{BigH}^+) _2 \right] \text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 26.39 ; Co, 14.61 ; H₂O, 8.92 per cent}.

14. *Oxalato-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium Oxalate* (cis).—The hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium hydroxide hydrate*, described by Ray and Ghosh (*loc. cit*), was neutralised by digestion with oxalic acid solution, added dropwise, till the supernatant liquid became slightly acidic to litmus. The sparingly soluble dark violet base

changed into the bluish violet prismatic needle-shaped crystals of the oxalate. The crystals were filtered, washed free from excess of oxalic acid with alcohol and finally dried in air. The substance is practically insoluble in water. {Found : Co, 13.60 ; C₂O₄, 30.52 ; H₂O (by loss at 95°), 8.41.

$[(C_2O_4)_4 \cdot Co (BigH^+)_2]_2 (C_2O_4)_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ requires Co, 13.74 ; C₂O₄, 30.77 ; H₂O, 8.39 per cent{.

The product obtained by drying to a constant weight at 95° gave on analysis : Co, 14.90 ; C₂O₄, 33.41. $[C_2O_4 \cdot Co (BigH^+)_2]_2 (C_2O_4)_4$ requires Co, 15.0 ; C₂O₄, 33.59 per cent{.

15. *Hydroxo-aquo cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Oxalate (trans)*.—*Trans* hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxide was obtained by the decomposition of the *trans*-hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate (*vide supra*) with the calculated amount of baryta solution. To the filtrate from barium sulphate, freed from Ba⁺⁺ or SO₄⁼⁼, a slight excess of oxalic acid was added in the form of a concentrated solution. The solution was then cooled in ice and treated with cold alcohol. The hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium oxalate separated in fine rose-coloured needle-shaped prismatic crystals. These were filtered, washed free from excess of oxalic acid with cold alcohol and finally dried in air. The substance is very soluble in water and the solution reacts acid to litmus. {Found : Co, 12.89 ; C₂O₄, 18.93.

$[(OH) (H_2O) Co (BigH^+)_2] C_2O_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ requires Co, 12.93 ; C₂O₄, 19.30 per cent{.

It might be of interest to mention here that an attempt to prepare the hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxide of the *trans* series from the corresponding chloride by treatment with moist silver oxide gave rise to an insoluble product and the filtrate was found absolutely free from all cobalt. This can be accounted for as follows :

Either, during the treatment with Ag₂O geometrical inversion occurs and the *trans*-hydroxide, first formed, immediately changes into the insoluble *cis*-isomer, or, the *trans*-base, first produced, unites with AgCl or excess of Ag₂O giving rise to the formation of a secondary complex which can be represented as

This can be compared with the monamine of AgCl ; the larger volume of the co-ordinating group (*i.e.*, cobalt bisbiguanide group) probably lowers the co-ordination number of silver, if we assume the chlorine or hydroxyl to be ionisable. Alternatively, it may be regarded as a non-ionisable compound with co-ordination number of silver equal to 2 as usual. Similar compounds were described by Rây

and Siddhanta with cobalt and chromium *trisbiguanidinium* hydroxides (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 298).

A solution of diammino-cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium* chloride gives precipitates of characteristic colour with many complex anions as described below.

- | | |
|--|---|
| 1. Potassium ferrocyanide
$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ | A cream coloured precipitate which turns buff on boiling and finally decomposes giving a red product. |
| 2. Potassium ferricyanide
$K_3Fe(CN)_6$ | A light green precipitate soluble in mineral acids, turns buff on boiling and becomes finally red |
| 3. Potassium cobalticyanide
$K_3Co(CN)_6$ | A light rose precipitate, soluble in acids. |
| 4. Potassium chromate
K_2CrO_4 | Light orange precipitate soluble in mineral acids. |
| 5. Potassium mercuri-iodide
K_2HgI_4 | A light rose precipitate soluble in hot water but reappears on cooling. |
| 6. Potassium bismuthi-iodide
$KBiI_4$ | A yellowish orange precipitate, insoluble in mineral acids but soluble in KI. |

Hydroxo-aquo and diaquo-cobaltic *bisbiguanidinium* chlorides give similar precipitates with the above-mentioned reagents.

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